

**IMPROVEMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM AND
INNOVATIVE APPROACH**

Vasieva Dilorom Ibragimovna,

Candidate of Historical Sciences,

Associate Professor

Karshi Engineering and Economics Institute

Abstract: In this article, the priorities of the radical reform of the higher education system of Uzbekistan in the years of independence, the fact that the socio-economic development of our country depends primarily on the training of well-educated and mature specialists, attention is focused on supporting education, which is the biggest investment for New Uzbekistan, Uzbekistan's international the position in education ratings, the changes that occurred as a result of reforms in higher education, the adoption of a number of regulatory documents in this regard, and the issues of gradually increasing the level of coverage of higher education were discussed.

Key words and concepts: independence, education, higher education, reform, education, quality of education, talent, human factor, intellectual potential, action strategy, Petition, State budget, globalization, information technology, modernization, financial independence, competitiveness, scientific research , culture, economic sectors, specialist, non-governmental education, state and society.

From the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been raised to the level of state policy, ensuring that our youth acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions corresponding to world standards, mature into physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities and talents, intellectual potential and effective work is being implemented to develop feelings of loyalty and devotion to our motherland in their hearts.

It is known that the "Strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", "On measures to further

expand the participation of economic sectors and sectors in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists" dated July 27, 2017, "Higher education" dated September 26, 2017 Decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev's Decree PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 "On Approving the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and June 5, 2018 "Addition on Improving the Quality of Education in Higher Education Institutions and Ensuring Their Active Participation in Comprehensive Reforms Implemented in the Country" on measures" PQ-2752 and on July 11, 2019 "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary special education" PQ-4391, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 3, 2019 " Decision 967 "On gradual transfer of higher education institutions to self-financing", Decree 133-f of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 25, 2019 serves as the basis for the radical reform of today's higher education system.

Indeed, education plays an important role in the development of society. In any field, specialists with high knowledge will have the opportunity to engage in scientific research developments, create new types of products, innovations and develop technologies.

One of the important directions of the Address of the President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev for 2023 was the educational policy. In his speech, the President said: "Improving the quality of education is the only correct way for the development of New Uzbekistan." First of all, we will focus on supporting education, which is the biggest investment for New Uzbekistan.

Funds allocated to education in Uzbekistan are increasing year by year. In particular, in 2021, it was planned to allocate 2,197 billion soums from the state budget to the education sector and 168 billion soums to science in order to implement the tasks set in the state programs, in particular, to implement the continuous education system and science development programs. This indicator in 2021 was 2.9 trillion soums for the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education and 22.1 trillion soums for the Ministry of Public Education. This year, 4.1 trillion soums will be allocated to the

Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, and 25.8 trillion soums to the Ministry of Public Education. In 2021, 98 billion soums were allocated for connecting schools to the Internet, and in 2022, 198 billion soums will be spent.

It can be confirmed with confidence that, according to the results of the World Bank general secondary education assessment, the quality of education in the country, which ranks 57th out of 174 countries with 474 points, is improving, and the system's assessment and assessment management capacity is being implemented at the level of international standards.

Globalization processes in the world and the current environment of deep competition between companies require specialists to be prepared for it. They not only provide favorable conditions for the development of their ideas and the practical implementation of the created theoretical models, but at the same time, they are also considered an important intellectual factor for the innovative development of the economy. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, systematic measures have been defined to further improve the education sector by training highly qualified specialists who have the skills to apply modern knowledge and pedagogical technologies and who contribute to the socio-economic development of our country and introduce advanced educational technologies in the field. Based on this, the results of the analysis of the supply of highly qualified personnel for the social sphere and economic sectors show that, first of all, it is necessary to increase the attention to the quality of personnel training for the education sector, to widely introduce advanced foreign experience in the field, and to improve the pedagogical education infrastructure.

Today, in the period of development of high technologies and informatization processes in the world, the competition between companies for the training of highly qualified specialists has somewhat increased. This applies not only to commercial organizations, but also to scientific research centers and educational institutions. In fact, the question of the quality of modern education is one of the problems that must be solved first. After all, the existing higher education institutions in our country will form the knowledge of specialists in a specific professional field in the future.

Higher education institutions serve the country's development in all aspects. The level of development of modern technologies based on the high level of intellectual resources and the competition of countries that want to own these resources serve as the main factor of not only economic, but also social and political progress. If we look at the top-ranked higher education institutions in the USA, European and Asian countries, which are the leading countries in terms of education, they are all located in developed countries, and it should be noted that they serve to further strengthen the position of their countries in the world community.

In the conditions of modern globalization, which is the demand of the time, all educational institutions are trying to ensure that the formation and development of the educational system in higher education institutions is in accordance with the new innovative conditions and the requirements of the economy. Factors affecting higher education institutions: firstly, the demand for graduate specialists is formed by organizations and enterprises, state institutions, and secondly, the conditions for applicants to enter higher education institutions are formed. Accordingly, educational institutions, in turn, influence the labor market and consumers in terms of employment of graduates with the necessary training in the professional field, and, accordingly, the demand for competitive specialists is constantly growing. Improving the quality of education in higher education institutions implies achieving the following goals:

- to improve the quality and efficiency of training specialists in higher education institutions;
- strengthening of relations between science, education and production;
- creation of infrastructure related to the implementation of innovative activities;
- development of innovative ideas based on the introduction of modern methods of training highly qualified specialists with higher education;
- continuous work and improvement of qualifications of professors and teachers working in higher education;
- effective organization of the financing mechanism of innovative activities in higher education institutions;

- continuous improvement of the educational process based on the use of innovations;

- education of students to master their chosen profession in depth, creatively and responsibly approach to solving professional issues is one of these.

In fact, it should be noted that higher education reforms in our country have risen to the level of state policy, because we understand that the level of higher education determines its future development. In accordance with this policy, issues related to the increase of the contingent of students and the number of higher education institutions, the quality of knowledge, new functions of higher education, the increase in the amount of information, and the wide spread of innovations were resolved. The current level of development of the society demands a new educational system - "innovative education" that is capable of building students' ability to plan for the future, a sense of responsibility for the future, and confidence in themselves and their professional abilities.

In order to increase the innovative potential of the higher education system, first of all, it is necessary to start with changing the social attitude towards higher educational institutions, to perceive them not only as a place of study, but also as institutions that create many new products, technologies and intangible assets of scientific ideas, science and scientists in the republic it is necessary to create mechanisms to show the reputation and results of their work to the general public. In their place, pedagogues-employees should not limit themselves to imparting knowledge to students, but should involve the movement of the most talented youth among them to solve actual scientific and technical problems. In addition, it will be necessary to review methods of incentives for scientists, inventors, participants of innovative activities. The issue of profiting from created innovations, intellectual property objects and distribution of property relations between higher education institutions and created pedagogues-employees is not clearly defined in the legislation. Establishing a system of benefits for private sector entities participating in the financing of scientific research activities will create a basis for attracting investments in this field. Wide involvement of higher education institutions in the development of

national and regional development programs against the background of large-scale reforms would mark a new stage in increasing their innovative potential. In order to maintain the high rate of economic development of our country, to achieve quantitative as well as qualitative indicators of development, we need to find and implement various unattracted factors and reserves, including the effective use of the wide opportunities and innovative potential of the higher education system.

Thus, today higher educational institutions are carrying out multi-stage innovative activities, innovative technologies are being introduced into the educational system at each stage of reforms, the scientific foundations of educational and educational technologies have been developed, and extensive experience of pedagogical innovations is being studied. In order to maintain the high rate of economic development of our country, to achieve quantitative as well as qualitative indicators of development, we need to find and implement various unattracted factors and reserves, including the effective use of the wide opportunities and innovative potential of the higher education system.

LIST OF USED REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. On measures to further improve the system of training of pedagogic personnel, retraining of public education workers and their qualification improvement // People's word, September 27, 2017, No. 77 (9038)
2. National database of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 24.09.2020, No. 1313
3. Teachers and coaches are our great strength, support and support in building a new Uzbekistan. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Mentors // Xalq sozi, 2020, October 1. - 207 (7709)
4. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PQ-2909 "On measures to further develop the higher education system".
5. National database of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 01.08.2018, No. 1269

6. National database of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 09.10.2019, No. 3887
7. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. December 22, 2022. – <https://review.uz/uz/post/>.
8. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. December 28, 2020. - www.uza.uz.
9. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be a daily rule of every leader's activity, www.press-service.uz